

History of Koykiryan Castle

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Abstract:

In the article, we consider the important priority of the monument of the Koykiryan fortress located in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the opinions expressed about the monument of the Koykiryan fortress, the analysis of the work done and carried out at the level of its research, which we should convey and leave to the future generation. we will be able to learn about cultural heritage objects in brief.

Keywords: Castle, moat, ruin, desert, building, ring, monument, population, river, Assurian, Zoroastrian, ancient.

The Koykiryan fortress is located 12 km north-east of the city of Tortkol. The layout is circular, surrounded by a wall, the total size is 86.5 m 0.6 ha. A two-story structure was built in the central part of the monument, a two-line defensive wall was built 44.4 m in circumference, 14.5 m away from the structure. The wall, in turn, has nine turrets, the entrance is located on the eastern wall. The gate has several roundabouts, a rectangular shape with a "Labyrinth", 18 m wide, and a total volume of 0.3 ha, strengthened by a semi-circular tower on both sides.

The castle is surrounded by a moat, 15 m wide and 3 m deep. The first floor of the central building consists of 8 rooms and its height is 8.5 m. The outer wall was first made of thatch, and then of raw bricks on all four sides, 7.2 m thick. The wall separating the rooms of the house is 0.6-1.9 m thick and made of raw brick. The height of the rooms is 3.6 m. The second floor continues through a covered corridor, the walls of which are covered with spears. The central building is entered from the east side through a ramp and is located on the second floor. The towers did not grow to the side, but slightly above the wall of the building. The gate is located on the eastern side of the outer wall. Monument S.P. It was discovered by the Khorezm expedition under the leadership of Tolstov, and excavations were carried out in 1951-1957. It has been determined that it belongs to the 4th century BC.

Karakalpakstan, Koyqrylan fortress

The ruins of thousands of castles are scattered in the vast expanses of Khorezm deserts, but the ruins of the Dead Sheep Castle - Koy-Qrilgan-kala are truly unique. The castle was accidentally discovered in 1938 by archaeologists of the Khorezm expedition.

Archaeologists were surprised, first of all, by the appearance of an ancient building that had never been seen in Khorezm: a mighty fortress with the remains of a defensive wall was not square or rectangular, as people saw, but round. Outside, the fortifications were in the form of a regular circle, in the center of which there was a castle, which was surrounded by an outer defensive wall with towers. The space between the central building and the wall - conventionally called the "ring", turned out to be completely built. The clay structure was huge: the diameter of the central building was 42 m,

Thousands of wonderful pieces of pottery are scattered on the sand dunes around the castle and its ruins. Based on them, as well as other finds, in particular, bronze arrowheads, it was possible to determine that the archaeologists had before them the oldest known monuments of Ancient Khorezm at that time. The oldest findings date back to the 4th and 3rd centuries.

In 1950, a new phase of excavations began in the castle ruins. As a result, it became known that the castle went through two stages of its development. The previous stage corresponds to IV-III centuries BC. The second period of the castle's life corresponds to the first centuries of our era. It was found that the central part of the fortress was destroyed by fire during the initial stages of development. Whether this was by accident or on purpose is still a mystery.

Kokhrilgan Castle is a strongly fortified fortress with several defensive walls that have been destroyed over time and can only be seen in a small area. Such fortifications are characteristic of all ancient and early medieval monuments of Khorezm.

According to archaeologists, "Dead Sheep Castle" is one of the most ancient monuments of the ancient Khorezm state, and it is a temple complex that partially served as the burial place of some ancient king or queen.

The inhabitants of the castle were Zoroastrians and worshiped Anakhita, the goddess of water and rivers, and Siovush, the god of the sun. The interesting thing about this monument is that there is a central complex. The western part of it was built in honor of the goddess Anakhita, and the eastern and southern parts were built in honor of the sun god Siovush, facing the sunrise, and the statues and fragments of pots with the images of the gods are proof of this.

The history of Kor-Krillgan-kala fortress goes back thousands of years. The remains of the oldest Assurians in Central Asia, paintings and writings in the ancient Khorezm language were found here. This fortress is still a mystery of history and is distinguished by its unique design among other fortresses of Ancient Khorezm.

On the wall of the fortified castle, there are special protruding towers typical of the style of construction of cities during the period of slavery in Central Asia, the Near and Middle East, and they have target holes for shooting arrows. There are farm buildings between the wall and the central building. A special trapezoidal brick was used for the porches. There is a gate in the eastern part of the castle, which is built in the form of a labyrinth in front of the gate.

There is a gate in the eastern part of the castle, which is built in the form of a labyrinth in front of the gate. The 2-story building in the center of the castle was built on special stairs. The roof of the house is flat. On the 1st floor, there are 8 separate vaulted rooms, in which ceramic coffins, dishes, oil vessels (hum and jugs) with various paintings, and decorative water tanks were found. Among the finds are terracotta figurines of deities, colorful wall paintings, and celestial objects. Ostodons are from burials, and inscriptions on pottery are dated. provides valuable information about the language and writings of the Khorezm people.

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